

Effect of Access to Green Jobs and Regulatory Incentives in Encouraging Sustainable Agricultural Practices Among Youth Agripreneurs in Southwest Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: Attention to green job creation and regulatory incentives as mechanisms to promote sustainable agricultural practices among youth agripreneurs has been limited in many regions, including Nigeria. This study evaluated the influence of access to green jobs and regulatory incentives on sustainable agricultural practices among youth agripreneurs in Southwest Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted and proportional stratified random sampling was employed to sample 369 respondents from a population of 9,099 youths involved in agribusiness projects supported by national and international development partners and managed by IITA in three selected states (Oyo, Ogun and Ekiti). Reliability tests of the research instruments yielded Cronbach's alpha values greater than 0.7. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis. Results revealed that access to green jobs ($\beta = 0.40$, $t = 8.30$, $p < 0.01$) and regulatory incentives ($\beta = 0.15$, $t = 3.18$, $p < 0.01$) had significant positive effects on the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices. The findings demonstrate that access to green jobs equips youth with critical skills for environmentally sustainable innovations, while regulatory incentives lower economic barriers, fostering the transition to sustainable agricultural practices. The study concluded that these factors are crucial for enabling sustainable agricultural practices among youth agripreneurs in Southwest Nigeria. It recommends expanding green job opportunities, streamlining regulatory processes and implementing integrated policy frameworks to institutionalize sustainability practices.

KEYWORDS: Youth access to green jobs, regulatory incentives, sustainable agricultural practices, Southwest Nigeria

I. INTRODUCTION

The economy of Nigeria heavily relies on various sectors, with key sectors such as the Agricultural sector driving both employment and national income (Olomu et al., 2020). However, traditional practices within these sectors have led to significant challenges, such as resource inefficiencies, operational constraints and environmental concerns, raising questions about long-term sustainability (Muhammad et al., 2020; Afolabi et al., 2022). Addressing these issues necessitates a transition to sustainable agricultural practices, which prioritize long-term productivity and environmental health (Çakmakçı et al., 2023). As global and national efforts to combat climate change intensify, sustainable agriculture has emerged as a critical pathway to ensuring food security and environmental resilience. Youth agripreneurs are key drivers of this transition due to their energy, adaptability and openness to innovation (Addo, 2018). Despite their potential, youth agripreneurs in Nigeria face significant challenges, such as limited access to resources, technical expertise and institutional support (Babu et al., 2020).

Interventions such as green job creation and regulatory incentives are increasingly recognized as strategies to enable youth agripreneurs to adopt sustainable agricultural practices (Mukwashi et al., 2024). Green jobs are defined as employment opportunities that contribute to environmental preservation offer income while equipping youth with skills and knowledge to implement sustainable techniques (Mwaura & Glover, 2021). These jobs encompass activities like organic farming, waste recycling and renewable energy use, fostering environmental stewardship among youth agripreneurs (International Labour Organisation (ILO), 2015). Regulatory incentives, including subsidies, grants, tax breaks and low-interest loans, are equally critical in lowering the economic barriers to adopting sustainable practices (Asuamah-Yeboah, 2024). For youth agripreneurs, these incentives reduce the costs associated with transitioning to sustainable inputs such as organic fertilizers or renewable energy systems, making eco-friendly practices more feasible and profitable. Regulatory frameworks also signal government commitment

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to sustainable agriculture, encouraging youth agripreneurs to integrate environmentally friendly methods into their operations (Sargani et al., 2020).

Southwest Nigeria, with its favorable demographic trends and emerging market opportunities, presents significant potential for sustainable economic development (Afolabi, 2015). However, traditional agricultural practices in the region continue to hinder progress, leading to challenges such as inefficiencies, environmental degradation and a lack of innovation (Kuyah et al., 2021). While sustainable business models, such as eco-friendly operations, resource-efficient technologies and circular economy principles, offer promising solutions, their adoption among the youth remains limited due to financial and technical barriers (Bashynska et al., 2024). Integrating green jobs and regulatory incentives into development strategies could help address these challenges. Green jobs not only foster capacity building and economic empowerment but also create pathways for youth to lead in sustainable agricultural practices while securing stable incomes (Aceleanu et al., 2015). Meanwhile, regulatory incentives can mitigate structural obstacles, making sustainable agricultural practices more accessible and financially feasible. Together, these approaches form a robust framework for fostering youth-driven enterprises that contribute to both environmental sustainability and economic growth.

This study examined the impact of access to green jobs and regulatory incentives on the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices among youth agripreneurs in Southwest Nigeria. The findings of this research will offer insights into how employment opportunities and policy frameworks can drive sustainable agricultural practices among youth, providing evidence-based recommendations for policymakers, development agencies and agricultural stakeholders. This study ultimately aims to support the design of effective strategies that empower youth agripreneurs, thereby promoting environmental sustainability and economic growth in Nigeria.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Sustainable agricultural practices

Sustainable agricultural practices represent a multidimensional approach to ensuring food security, environmental conservation and economic viability. Rooted in the concept of meeting present needs without compromising future resources, sustainable agriculture emerged significantly during the "Green Revolution," transitioning global food systems toward higher productivity while maintaining ecological balance (Ojadi, 2023). This approach integrates the preservation of natural resources like soil, water and biodiversity with practices such as crop rotation, organic farming and precision agriculture to ensure long-term viability (Adigun et al., 2017; Bathaei & Streimikiene, 2023). In the Nigerian context, achieving sustainability has been a complex process marked by progress in some areas and persistent challenges such as land degradation, improper pesticide use and wastewater management (Ufiobor, 2017). Agribusiness, which utilizes approximately 40% of the world's land and 70% of terrestrial water resources, remains a cornerstone of sustainability efforts, balancing food production needs with environmental conservation amid growing resource competition (Rosano-Pena et al., 2014; Hinson et al., 2019).

The key dimensions of sustainability (social, economic and ecological) highlight the need for a comprehensive perspective. Social sustainability focuses on fostering supportive environments and stakeholder collaboration, particularly for youth in agribusiness (Janker et al., 2019; Scheurich et al., 2021). Economic sustainability emphasizes profitability, liquidity and productivity as benchmarks for long-term viability while addressing price variability and regulatory challenges (Van Calker et al., 2007; Osazefua, 2020). Ecologically, sustainable agriculture prioritizes soil health, water conservation and climate-smart practices to mitigate environmental degradation and combat climate change (Cakmakci et al., 2023; Lebacqz et al., 2013). By addressing these interconnected aspects, youth agribusiness training programs in Southwest Nigeria aim to balance productivity with environmental care, building a resilient agricultural sector that sustains livelihoods today and safeguards resources for the future.

Access to green jobs

The transition to a green economy not only promotes environmental sustainability but is also expected to create green jobs in all economic sectors, including agriculture, forestry and fisheries (Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), 2010). The United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) defines a green job as work in agricultural, manufacturing, research and development (R&D), administrative and service activities that contribute(s) substantially to preserving or restoring environmental quality. It includes jobs that reduce energy, materials and water consumption through high efficiency strategies; de-carbonize the economy and minimize or altogether avoid generation of all forms of waste and pollution". Green jobs align with the International Labour Organisation (ILO) principles of decent work, emphasizing freedom, equity, security and human dignity for both genders (ILO, 2013). The ILO's Decent Work Agenda, influencing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), includes employment creation, social protection, rights at work and social dialogue (ILO, 2015). SDG Goal 8 promotes sustained economic growth, full employment and decent work, with a focus on youth employment and MSME formalisation in the informal sector (ILO, 2015). Target 8.2 underscores labour-intensive sectors, productivity enhancement, technological upgrading, innovation and value

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addition, suggesting green jobs contribute to these goals while ensuring environmental sustainability and workers' rights (ILO, 2015).

Across the globe, a significant number of environmentally friendly jobs have already emerged, as reported by the ILO and the UNEP in 2012. The establishment of such jobs presents promising prospects for youths in both developed and developing nations to engage in more sustainable economies. However, it is crucial to note that the enthusiasm of youth to participate in these green economies does not guarantee immediate employment. Youth encounter various challenges in accessing these opportunities, with skills development being a prominent issue. It is necessary for them to acquire the required skills or enhance existing ones, especially considering the demands of a job market that often requires specific expertise (FAO & IFAD, 2014).

Regulatory incentives

The Oxford dictionary defines incentive as something that motivates or encourages someone to do something. This definition underscores the importance of incentives in motivating youths to engage in agribusiness, which, in turn, supports sustainable agricultural practices. It is essential to note that incentives for youth involvement in agribusiness extend beyond financial support alone (Bello et al., 2021). Unfortunately, a common misconception prevails that incentives are limited to monetary terms. This narrow perspective has led to insufficient attention being given to other critical areas where regulatory authorities or development partners could provide incentives. For instance, beyond financial backing, youths engaged in agribusiness or participating in agribusiness training programs organized by regulatory authorities or development partners could benefit from non-monetary incentives.

One such non-monetary incentive is the facilitation of a more straightforward and less bureaucratic business registration process for youths (Batanova, 2024). This could involve providing reduced costs for the registration of their agribusiness ventures and creating pathways that alleviate the rigorous bureaucratic procedures involved. Moreover, the provision of incentives should not be restricted to business registration alone. Other areas, such as the reduction in costs for essential inputs like fertilizers and other agricultural raw materials tailored specifically for the youth demographic, are equally important. Recognizing and addressing the misconception that incentives are solely financial opens up avenues for a more comprehensive and effective approach to supporting youth agribusiness (Babu et al., 2021). By considering a broader spectrum of incentives, including streamlined registration processes and reduced input costs, regulatory authorities and development partners can significantly contribute to the success of youth agribusiness training programs and consequently, sustainable agricultural practices in Nigeria.

B. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study utilized the Theory of Change (Chen, 1990; Coryn et al., 2011) and Empowerment Theory (Rappaport, 1981; Zimmerman, 1995) as foundational frameworks. These theories were chosen because their perspectives align closely with the study's focus and the variables under investigation. The Theory of Change posits that social programs achieve desired outcomes through a series of interconnected events. It emphasizes that identifying and mapping the causal linkages between program activities and outcomes is critical, with the success of such programs relying on well-defined goals, active stakeholder engagement and ongoing evaluation to enhance effectiveness (Weiss, 1995). Empowerment Theory, on the other hand, is grounded in the belief that individuals, such as youth in agribusiness, possess latent potential and capabilities that can be activated through targeted interventions. This theory highlights the importance of fostering a sense of self-efficacy, control and agency among individuals to achieve positive outcomes. Furthermore, it suggests that transformative change can be facilitated by creating supportive environments and providing access to resources and information (Rappaport, 1981; Zimmerman, 1995).

III. METHODS

A. Research Design

This study adopts a cross-sectional survey research design which facilitated the use of a structured research instrument in collecting data from respondents. A proportional stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representative sampling. Data analysis involved both descriptive statistics (presented using bar charts) and inferential statistics (performed through multiple regression analysis).

B. Population of the Study

The target population for this study comprised 9,099 (nine thousand and ninety-nine) youths who participated in youth-centered agribusiness projects and programs funded by national and international development partners and implemented by IITA across three selected states (Oyo, Ogun and Ekiti). The sample size for the research was determined using Taherdoost's (2017) guidelines, which are based on Yamane's (1967) formula for large populations. According to these guidelines, a sample size of 369 was recommended for this study.

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C. Reliability of Research Instrument

A pilot survey involving 37 youth agripreneurs, representing 10% of the total sample size, was conducted to evaluate and validate the research instrument. The collected responses were analyzed to determine the instrument's reliability. The findings from the pilot study confirmed the instrument's reliability, as the Cronbach's alpha values for all variables exceeded 0.70.

D. Model Specification

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + e \quad (1)$$

Where: Y = Sustainable Agribusiness Practices (SAP)

($\beta_i, i=0, 1, 2, 3, 4$) = various coefficients for the independent variables

X1= Access to green jobs

X2 = Regulatory incentives

X3= Age of the respondent (years)

X4= Gender (Male or Female)

X5= Educational background (No formal education, Primary education, Secondary education, Vocational/Technical Training, Graduate or Postgraduate)

e = Error Term

IV. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

H₀: Access to green jobs and regulatory incentives have no significant effect on sustainable agricultural practices in Southwest Nigeria.

To test this hypothesis, a multiple linear regression analysis was performed. The independent variables (access to green jobs and regulatory incentives) were analyzed alongside demographic factors (age, gender and educational level) to evaluate their combined effect on the dependent variable, sustainable agricultural practices. Responses to all items under access to green jobs were combined to generate a composite score, as well as responses under regulatory incentives. Similarly, responses related to sustainable agricultural practices were aggregated into a composite index. The results of the regression analysis, including parameter estimates, are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis of the Effect of Access to Green Jobs and Regulatory Incentives on Sustainable Agricultural Practices

N	Model	B	Sig.	T	ANOVA (Sig.)	R	Adjusted R ²	F (5, 363)
369	Access to Green Job	0.40	0.00**	8.30	0.00*	0.695	0.518	20.23
	Regulatory incentives	0.15	0.00**	3.18				
	Age	0.03	0.61	0.51				
	Gender	0.04	0.42	0.81				
	Educational level	0.02	0.00**	3.38				
	Constant	2.95	0.00**	7.24				
	Predictors: Access to Green Job, Regulatory incentives, Age, Gender and Educational level							
Dependent Variable: Sustainable Agricultural Practices								

Source: Researcher's Field Results, 2024. *Significant at 5%, ** Significant at 1%

The results in Table 1 revealed that access to green jobs ($\beta = 0.40, t = 8.30, p < 0.01$) and regulatory incentives ($\beta = 0.15, t = 3.18, p < 0.01$) had a positive and statistically significant effect on sustainable agricultural practices. This suggests that both access to green jobs and regulatory incentives significantly contribute to promoting sustainable agricultural practices. Additionally, educational level ($\beta = 0.02, t = 3.38, p < 0.01$) also showed a positive and significant effect on sustainable agricultural practices. However, Age ($\beta = 0.03, t = 0.51, p = 0.61$) and Gender ($\beta = 0.04, t = 0.81, p = 0.42$) did not have statistically significant effects. The model showed an R value of 0.695, indicating a strong positive relationship between the predictors and sustainable agricultural practices. The adjusted R² value of 0.518 suggests that approximately 51.8% of the variation in sustainable agricultural practices is explained by the predictors, with the remaining 48.2% attributable to other factors outside the model. The F-statistic (df = 5, 363) = 20.23, with $p < 0.05$, confirms that the overall model is statistically significant.

The regression equation is expressed as:

$$Y = 2.95 + 0.40X_1 + 0.15X_2 + 0.03X_3 + 0.04X_4 + 0.02X_5 + e \quad (2)$$

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Where:

Y = Sustainable Agribusiness Practices (SAP)

X₁ = Access to Green Jobs

X₂ = Regulatory Incentives

X₃ = Age of the respondent (years)

X₄ = Gender (Male or Female)

X₅ = Educational level (Primary School Leaving Certificate, SSCE/WAEC, OND/NCE, BSC/HND or Postgraduate)

e = Error Term

From the above regression equation, it was revealed that access to green jobs, regulatory incentives and educational level are key determinants in promoting sustainable agricultural practices among youth agribusiness training participants. Specifically, for every 1-unit increase in access to green jobs, while keeping other variables constant, sustainable agricultural practices increase by 0.40 units. Similarly, for every 1-unit increase in regulatory incentives, sustainable agricultural practices increase by 0.15 units, all other variables being kept constant. The results indicate that the null hypothesis (H₀), which posits no significant effect of access to green jobs and regulatory incentives on sustainable agricultural practices, is rejected.

V. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study highlights the significant positive impact of access to green jobs on youth adoption of sustainable agricultural practices, emphasizing their role in equipping youth with skills critical for resource efficiency and eco-friendly innovation. This aligns with Uduji et al. (2020), who identified green jobs as a pathway for fostering environmental responsibility and enhancing productivity. These findings resonate with empowerment theory, which underscores the importance of equipping individuals with the capacity and opportunities to make meaningful changes in their environment. Similarly, the theory of change offers a lens to understand how exposure to environmentally conscious work translates into long-term behavioral shifts, as it links inputs like training and mentorship to measurable outcomes in sustainable practices. Lang et al. (2022) further illuminate this finding, suggesting that green jobs act as conduits for embedding youth within communities that prioritize sustainability. By fostering mentorship, collaboration and a sense of belonging, green jobs create an environment where sustainable agricultural practices are not only learned but reinforced through social and professional networks, thereby driving sustained behavioral change.

The study also showed that regulatory incentives, such as subsidies and tax reliefs, significantly influence youth in agribusiness to adopt sustainable agricultural practices by reducing cost barriers, aligning with Ikuemonisan et al. (2022). However, as noted by Panez et al. (2020), Alawode et al. (2019) and Addo (2018), short-term incentives alone may not drive lasting change without integration into broader policy frameworks. Empowerment Theory further reinforces the importance of aligning regulatory incentives with supportive policies to sustain their impact. This highlights the need for comprehensive approaches that pair incentives with regulatory frameworks, training programs and long-term support systems to institutionalize sustainability. These findings emphasize that while regulatory incentives are valuable for initiating engagement, their long-term efficacy depends on being part of an integrated strategy fostering sustainable agricultural development.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the empirical findings, the study concludes that access to green jobs and regulatory incentives have a significant impact on the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices among youth agripreneurs in Southwest Nigeria.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, youth access to green jobs significantly influences the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices among youth agripreneurs in Southwest Nigeria. The study therefore recommends expanding green job opportunities in agriculture and incorporating eco-friendly skills into youth training programs to promote long-term sustainability. Additionally, the study highlights the role of regulatory incentives in encouraging youth participation in sustainable agriculture. It is also recommended that tax breaks, simplified business registration and faster approval processes be introduced to reduce bureaucratic delays, thereby supporting environmentally friendly agribusinesses and economic growth.

VIII. SUGGESTION FOR FURTHER STUDIES

Future research could explore using a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative techniques, along with a longitudinal design, to gain deeper insights into individual experiences and better understand the personal and socio-cultural factors that influence sustainable agricultural practices over time.

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